

Discovery of M-dwarf Flares from SkyMapper Southern Survey

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Abstract

- M-dwarf flares are common candidates of high-amplitude, fast optical transients serendipitously discovered by many time-domain surveys. We present the results of our search to constrain the flaring fraction or occurrence rate of these galactic transients in a flux-limited sample (complete to 18 mag in all *uvgriz* bands) from SkyMapper southern survey.
- By covering a large sky area homogeneously with a six-colour sequence, it allows us to assemble bona-fide flares on timescales of less than four minutes for each pointing. We apply a correlation-based outlier search to identify flaring epochs in the light curves of M dwarfs.
- In this work, we investigate in detail how the observed flare rate is sensitive to colour (spectral type) or vertical distance from the galactic plane with Gaia DR2 catalogue.

SkyMapper Shallow Survey: DR1.1

The SkyMapper First Data Release provides data from the Shallow Survey component across >98% of the southern sky that were observed between March 2014 and September 2015 (Wolf+ 2018).

- Each visit to a given field includes an exposure in full six-filter sequence of [*u-v-g-r-i-z*], referred to as "observation block": 2~12 visits per object.
- Enough time to cover flare evolution: $\Delta t_{uvgriz} < 4$ min (exposure times of 40, 20, 5, 5, 10 and 20 sec, respectively)

Figure 1. Time-resolved flare spectra of YZ CMi (Kowalski+ 2013) with SkyMapper filter curves. Enhanced blue continuum and emission lines are stronger in our blue filters.

- Volume-limited: 622 M dwarfs (M0V-M9.5V; Winters+ 2015)
- Flux-limited: 1,406,575 sources using *riz* colour cuts with $E(B-V) < 0.2$. There is a distance limit less than 1.5 kpc (Gaia DR2 estimation; Lindegren+ 2018)

Figure 2. De-reddened colour-colour diagram of volume- (<25pc) and flux-limited ($r < 18$) samples for M dwarfs (Image credit: <http://skymapper.anu.edu.au/sky-viewer/>).

Correlation-based outlier detection: dm-dt-filter

We utilize a flare variability index Φ to search for flaring epochs from consecutive filter pairs in each observation block n that was previously used by other photometric searches (e.g., Kowalski+ 2009, Davenport+ 2012), as follows:

$$\Phi_{uv}(n) = \left[\frac{m_u(n) - \langle m_u \rangle}{\sigma_u(n)} \right] \left[\frac{m_v(n) - \langle m_v \rangle}{\sigma_v(n)} \right],$$

$m(n)$: PSF magnitude at epoch n
 $\langle m \rangle$: quiescent magnitude
 $\sigma(n)$: measurement error at epoch n .

Figure 3. Distribution between flare variability index and amplitude variation with the most sensitive filter pair.

High-amplitude, powerful flares: $\Delta u > 3 \sim 7$ mag

Using different detection thresholds for dm-dt-filter parameter space, we identified ~250 flare candidates from 4,417,082 observation blocks in the full filter pairs (i.e., $\Phi_{uv} + \Phi_{vg} + \Phi_{gr} + \Phi_{ri} + \Phi_{iz}$). Our random imaging sometimes catches fast, impulsive-phase flares which exhibit u-band enhancements up to $\Delta u \sim 7$ mag.

Figure 4. Light curves of three high-amplitude flares from the SkyMapper DR1.1 and their multi-band image cut-outs before and after flaring (yellow arrow).

Flaring fraction: colour and Z

We investigate the fraction of SkyMapper M dwarfs that have detected flares that shows:

- A trend of increasing flaring fraction with increasing colour as shown from previous photometric investigations (e.g., Kowalski+ 2009, Davenport+ 2016),
- Strong dependence of the flaring fraction on vertical distance, Z , from the Galactic plane (see also Kowalski+ 2009, West+ 2011),
- Flare duty cycle also increases with increasing colour and decreasing $|Z|$ as expected, which is a similar trend seen in the SDSS photometric and spectroscopic observations (see Kowalski+ 2009, Hilton+ 2010).

Figure 5. Fraction of flaring stars as a function of Gaia BP-RP colour (left) and as a function of vertical distance, Z , from the galactic plane (right), respectively. Error bars are 68% confidence level of binomial distribution.

Figure 6. Flare duty cycle (flaring percentage during the entire period of observations) as a function of colour (left) and vertical distance from the plane (right).

New SkyMapper Data Release 2 will coming soon (Oct 2018) which includes the nearly full Main Survey data (up to mid-March 2018). It will help us to discover more high-amplitude flares and to quantify their flaring properties accurately.

References

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